

NATIONAL AND EXPERIENCE IN TEACHING TOURISM TERMS

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Abstract. This article highlights the importance of national and foreign experiences in the teaching of terms related to the field of tourism, and the fact that many important works aimed at increasing the level of national experiences based on foreign experiences are being put into practice.

Key words: MICE-tourism, compensation, art of giving, tourist, budget, functional-semantic, lexical-semantic.

НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ

Аннотация. В статье подчеркивается важность национального и зарубежного опыта преподавания терминов, связанных со сферой туризма, и тот факт, что многие важные работы, направленные на повышение уровня национального опыта на основе зарубежного опыта, внедряются в практику.

Ключевые слова: MICE-туризм, компенсация, искусство дарения, турист, бюджет, функционально-семантический, лексико-семантический.

In order to develop the tourist infrastructure, to meet the demand caused by the sharp increase in the number of tourists, the state has implemented complex measures to increase accommodation facilities.

First, 22 types of redundant requirements regulating the operation of hostels belonging to the type of affordable accommodation facilities have been abolished. Also, the procedure for mandatory certification of hotel services provided by hostels was canceled, and the practice of conducting work after being registered in the unified register of guest houses and hostels was established

Secondly, in order to increase the number of small hotels in the country, 8 sample projects of small hotels with up to 50 rooms, based on the experience of South Korea and Turkey, were presented to entrepreneurs free of charge. When calculated, the total cost of distributed projects is 60 billion. is more than soum.

Thirdly, in order to attract foreign investments in the field of tourism, a number of incentives were introduced for the construction of hotels based on the conditions of public-private partnership. According to this, for each room of the built 3-star hotels, 30 mln., 40 mln. for 4-star hotels will be allocated from the state budget. It was decided to allocate compensation of soums.

At the same time, the practice of partially compensating the royalties of hotels that have attracted world-famous hotel brands has been introduced. Accordingly, 200 USD will be allocated for each room of 3-star hotels, 400 USD for 4-star hotels.

As a result, the number of deployment tools has increased dramatically. In particular, between 2016 and 2020, their number increased from 750 to 1,308, and the number of available

places increased from 34,000 to 62,000. Also, during 2018-2020, the number of guest houses increased 13 times and reached 1386.

MICE-tourism. According to the estimates of the World Tourism Organization, a business tourist spends 3-4 times more during his trip than a leisure tourist. In addition, while leisure tourism is seasonal, business tourism has the potential to generate income throughout the year.

In recent years, practical measures have been taken to diversify the composition of tourism services and develop new types of tourism in Uzbekistan. In particular, MICE tourism, that is, in Uzbekistan, a lot of attention is paid to increasing the flow of tourists by organizing various meetings, conferences and exhibitions.

Sports tournament "Game of Braves" traditionally held in Khorezm, "Bakhshchilik art" festival in Surkhandarya, "Moynaq-2019" car rally competitions were organized in Karakalpakstan. Therefore, a plan of measures for the development of MICE-tourism in Uzbekistan was developed and approved by the Cabinet of Ministers.

The lexical system of the language is considered a specific whole, which consists of "thematic groups" united under a common content. Each thematic group unites a number of lexical-semantic groups.

Each member of a group united to a lexical-semantic group on the basis of a certain sign must repeat the theme that is the basis for joining this group. In turn, the lexical-semantic groups in the language system consist of certain lexical lines. The lexemes that make up one lexical line should also have a certain common sign - a unifying (integral) sema, and lexemes in these lines should be separated from each other by mutually different (differential) sema.

Terms are also classified lexically-semantically as a special lexical unit. In particular, Uzbek language tourist terms are initially divided into several thematic groups according to their content, function, and comprehensiveness. These thematic groups are further divided into lexical-semantic groups.

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